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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. A MOHAMMAD ADHIL has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ABHINAV U K has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADITI SASHI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADITI SHAILESH NAIK has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADNAN P P has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADWAITH SUNILKUMAR has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AFRAA MARIYUM has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AFREEN MUJEEB SHEIKH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AISWARYA P G has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AJAY KRISHNA B has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AKHIYA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AKSHATHA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AKSHAY GIREESH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ALBIN MATHEW SHAJI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ALISHA SHYLESH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AMAL SHINE K J has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AMBIKA SARASHETTI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AMINATH MASHOODA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANSIFA K M has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ANUGRAH THOMAS SALU has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ARYA ANAND has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ASHWINI SAHITHYA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AYISHATHUL FARHANA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BASTIN THOMAS has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. BOBY V JOHN has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHENGA TSOMO has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHINNU SURESH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. CHRISTO KURIAKOSE has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DEEKSHA P R has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DEVRAG SATHIAN PULLARIKAL has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DHANRAJ PRABHU has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DODDI MANI VARDHAN REDDY has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DON JACOB has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FATHIMATH HIBHA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. FEMINA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. H KUSHI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HAVAS MUHAMMED has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. HRITHIKESH K JAYAISHAN has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JACKSON SHAJI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KAMBLE TANISHKA VIRESH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. KARTHIKA AJIKUMAR has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. LIKHITHA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MARUVINA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MELVIN SAMUEL has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MIDHUN MOHAN A K has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOMIN ANUSHA MOHD MUSLIM has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PRAGNA K N has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PRANEETH KUMAR HEGDE has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RAICHURI AMAANAHMED ABDUL REHMAN has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RAKSHA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RICHARD JOBY has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RINKU KUMARI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. RITESH BHASKAR POOJARI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ROSHAN ANTONY has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ROSHIMA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. S SHEFA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SACHIN R KARABARI has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAFEL SURESH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAFOORA BEEVI M has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAHIDHA N has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SALINI S has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHARVARY K G has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHERIN MARY JAMES has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHILPA A has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHRADHA S has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SOWJANYA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SUJAYASHREE has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SUNAINA has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SURAJ M NAREGAL has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SUSHANT GAJANAN MOGER has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SUSHMITHA S KOTIAN has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SWEJAL SAKHARAM GAWAS has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SYCRATE JOSEPH has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. TESSA SUSAN JOY has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VILANILATH THOMAS BENN SAM has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VISHNU PRIYA P has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VISHWAKARMA SHRADDHA YOGESH has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. VIYUHA MURINGATHARA CHERIAN has completed his/her mini project on
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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SINCHANA P P has completed his/her mini project on “**Chart Making in Exercise Therapy**” in the third semester of the BPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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